

NATURAL DYE EXTRACTION AND ANTIMICROBIAL ASSESSMENT FROM PEA FLOWERS

¹Iram Muzaffar Bhokare, ²Shruti Mangesh Sutar, ³Suryakant Sukumar Wadkar,
^{4*}Vandana Ramchandra Dongare

^{1,2,3,4*}Department of biotechnology, Smt. Kasturbai Walachand Arts and Science College,
Sangli, 416416. (M.S.) India.

Article Received on
12 August 2025,

Revised on 02 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 22 Sept. 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17223791>

***Corresponding Author**

**Vandana Ramchandra
Dongare**

Department of
biotechnology, Smt.
Kasturbai Walachand Arts
and Science College,
Sangli, 416416. (M.S.)
India.

ABSTRACT

The main advantage of extraction of natural dye from plant sources over the chemically synthesized dye is to prevent environmental pollution. The effluents obtained from synthetically used dyes in textile industry occurs problem during manufacturing and causes pollution. But the use of natural dyes from plants offers an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic dyes, which are often associated with environmental pollution and health risks. This study investigates the extraction of natural dye from Pea Flowers and evaluates antimicrobial properties. Three different methods applied for the extraction of natural dye such as aqueous extraction by maceration process for 7 days, extraction by boiling method and aqueous extraction by maceration process for 1 hr at normal temperature. Ethanolic extract was prepared for the determination of antimicrobial properties. The dyes produced were dyed on cotton cloth and tested for their color fastness to washing properties. Colour absorption property measured in colorimeter at different wavelength in the range 400-700nm. Among the three extracts,

higher colour intensity observed for aqueous extract of 7 days. All the three extracts stain cotton cloth without mordents. Phytochemical analysis of Aqueous extract showed presence of proteins, carbohydrate, total phenols and flavonoids and absence of tanins. Ethanolic extract inhibit the growth of both gram positive (*S.aureus*) and gram negative bacteria (*E.coli*).

KEYWORDS: Natural Dyes, Antimicrobial, Biodegradable, Pea Flower.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, environmental protection has become a significant challenge for the textile industry due to its extensive use of chemicals for colouring fabrics. These chemicals are not only harmful to the environment but also pose health risks to humans. Synthetic dyes, in particular, have many disadvantages, and some have even been found to be carcinogenic and mutagenic, leading to their ban in several countries. On the other hand, floral dyes hold great importance in textile dyeing. They provide natural pigments that impart beautiful colours to fabrics and also offer a pleasant fragrance. This fragrance helps in keeping the textile material fresh for longer durations by masking body odour, thus enhancing the overall comfort and appeal of the garment.^[1] Dyes derived from flowers are environmentally friendly, economical, and contribute to maintaining ecological balance. Almost all flowers with vibrant colours can release dyes when boiled in a dye bath. However, while many of these floral dyes impart colour, they often lack strong affinity towards textile materials. Only a few specific flowering plants yield dyes that can produce long-lasting and permanent colours on fabrics. Some examples of such dye-yielding flowers are *Celosia cristata* Gulmohar, Rose, Hibiscus.^[2]

Clitoria ternatea L., commonly known as butterfly pea and belonging to the Fabaceae family, is a plant of significant interest due to its wide range of applications across various industries, particularly in medicine, food, cosmetics, and textile dyeing. The plant's flowers are rich in anthocyanins—natural water-soluble pigments responsible for vivid blue to purple coloration, which are not only visually appealing but also offer multiple health benefits, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and cytotoxic properties.^[3] Compounds reported to be found in the flowers are ternatin anthocyanins and various flavanol glycosides of kaempferol, quercetin and myricetin.^[4] and treatment of human diseases. This study aims to explore the extraction of natural dyes from butterfly flower, assess their antimicrobial potential, and identify the phytochemicals that contribute to these properties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

Ethanol, Nutrient agar, DMSO, Benedict's reagent, Biuret reagent, Ninhydrin, Hungers reagent, Wagner's reagent, lead acetate, H₂SO₄ etc. Molish reagent, 5% Ferric chloride, 10%

Alcoholic Ferric Chloride, 10% NAOH, Glacial Acetic Acid, Chloroform. All chemicals used for the study were of AR grade and purchased locally.

Plant materials

Clitoria ternatea plant was collected locally and authenticated by the Department of Botany Smt.Kasturbai Walchand College of Arts and Science, Sangli.

Extract preparation

Clitoria ternatea flowers were collected from well grown plant. Collected flowers were washed thoroughly with running tap water then with distilled water and dried at room shade for a week. Then it was homogenized to a fine powder and stored in an airtight glass container, protected from sunlight, stored at 4 °C until the further process.

Preparation of Dye

1) Aqueous Extraction of *C. ternatea*

10gm of powder was immersed in Flask containing 100ml D/W and 10ml Chloroform. This mixture was placed on rotary shaker for 7 days and maceration process was carried out. After maceration was completed the extract was filtered using Whatman no.1 filter paper. The obtained extract was subjected to determination of phytochemical constituents.^[5]

2) Extraction by boiling

3.3gm plant material (powdered) was immersed in 70ml distilled water and boiled for 1 hour.^[6]

3) Preparation of aqueous extract at normal temperature

3.3 gm plant material (powdered) in 70ml distilled water and kept on shaker for 1 hour at RT. All the above three extracts were filtered through whatmans filter paper no. 1 Filtrates were kept in refrigerator for investigation of dyeing properties. Only 7 days aqueous extract used for phytochemical analysis.

4) Ethanolic Extraction of *C.ternatea*

10gm of powder was suspended in flask containing 100ml ethanol. This mixture was placed on rotary shaker for 7 days and maceration process was carried out. After maceration was completed the extract was filtered using Whatman no.1 filter paper. Extract was concentrated by complete evaporation of ethanol and used for screening of antimicrobial properties.

Phytochemicals Investigation

Phytochemicals are the chemicals that are naturally present in plants. These phytochemicals are of great interest now a days due its great medicinal values and its application in various fields. Phytochemicals play a crucial role against number of diseases such as asthma, arthritis, cancer etc. unlike pharmaceutical chemicals that are used these phytochemicals do not have any side effects. Since the phytochemicals cure diseases without causing any harm to human beings these can also be considered as “man friendly medicines”. Therefore to check presence of different phytochemicals various qualitative test were carried out.

Preliminary qualitative analysis

1) Test for Alkaloids : Mayer’s test

To a few ml of plant sample extract, two drops of Mayer’s reagent are added along the sides of test tube. Appearance of white creamy precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2) Test for Carbohydrates : Benedict’s test

To 0.5 ml of extract, 0.5 ml of Benedict’s reagent is added. The mixture is heated on a boiling water bath for 2 minutes. A characteristic coloured precipitate indicates the presence of sugar.

3) Test for Flavonoids: Lead acetate test and H₂SO₄ test

The extract (50 mg) is dissolved in of distilled water and to this 3 ml of 10% lead acetate solution is added. A bulky white precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

To 3ml of extract, 1ml of conc, H₂SO₄ is added. Blood orange colour indicates the presence of flavonoids.

4) Test for Tannins: Alkaline reagent test

An aqueous solution of the extract is treated with 10% ammonium hydroxide solution. Yellow fluorescence indicates the presence of flavonoids.^[7, 8]

Colour absorbtion property

Colour absorbtion property measured in colorimeter at different wavelegth in the range 400-700nm.

Preparation of the cloth

The cloth material (cotton) is cut into small pieces (10*10 cm) and it is dissolved in sodium hydroxide and refluxed for 15 minutes to remove the starch; cellulose and other dirt particles from it.

The cloth treated with sodium hydroxide was put in the mordant solution and simmered for 15 minutes and then it is taken out.

Application of dye to fabrics: The dye is applied to fabric by two methods, with mordents and without mordents. We have applied dye to fabric by without mordent method.

Without mordant: The fabric which is treated with sodium hydroxide is directly immersed at the dye bath and the fabric is simmered for half an hour. After the dye enters through the cloth. The cloth is taken out and dried for further studies.^[9]

Assay for Antimicrobial activity

Ethanol extract of *C. ternatea* were tested for antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The stock solution was prepared at a concentration of 5mg of dried Ethanol Extract suspended in 1ml DMSO (5%). The antimicrobial activity was experimented by agar well diffusion method. Wells of 5mm diameter were made with sterile borer after the solidification of Petri plates prefilled with Nutrient agar and fresh inoculum of organisms. The wells were then filled with 5mg/ml stock solution at 25ul, of concentrations of extracts. Antimicrobial assay plates were incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. After incubation, the zones of inhibition diameter around each of well were measured.^[3]

Dyeing Properties

The cloth sample were dyed with different aqueous extract in a ratio 1:2. The dye extracts was prepared by adding 10ml extracted dye in 20 ml Distilled water.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The different colour shades were obtained from flower extracts of butter pea. These extracts show variation in colour which mainly depends upon the nature of extraction solvents as shown in fig.1.

Fig. 1: Photograph of three coloured shades of different extracts.

All three extracts exhibited considerable colour intensity, as observed in the photograph. Notably, the extract prepared via keeping seven days on shaker highest colour intensity among the three, indicating that seven days aqueous extraction may enhance pigment yield compared to the other methods as shown in fig.1.

Aqueous extraction of dyes offers significant advantages such as simplicity, low cost, and environmental friendliness. However, it also has certain limitations, including low yield, poor colourfastness, and potential dye degradation during boiling. In the textile industry, natural dyes are valued for their eco-friendly nature, biodegradability, and their aesthetic and cultural relevance. These dyes can be applied to various fabrics, including cotton, silk, wool, and linen. Beyond textiles, natural dyes have applications in the food and cosmetic industries as well. For instance, beetroot extract is widely used as a natural food colouring, while henna serves as a cosmetic dye for hair and skin. Additionally, natural dyes hold importance in traditional medicine due to their therapeutic properties.^[10] Advantage of natural dye usually biodegradable and renewable also Non-toxic, non-allergic and non-carcinogenic as these are obtained from animals or vegetable matters without any chemical processing Easy to extract and purify No disposal problems with natural dye waste Colours produced by natural dyes are usually soft, lustrous and soothing to the eyes.^[11] The present investigation carried on the *Clitorea ternatea* covered the presence of therapeutic active constituents. The phytochemically active compounds of *Clitorea ternatea* were qualitatively investigated and results are displayed below. Qualitative analysis of aqueous extract obtained via seven days staying the presence of carbohydrate, protein, total phenols and flavonoids and absence of tannin as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Qualitative analysis of Phytochemicals “–“Absence and “+” Present.

Phytochemical	Test	Result
Tannin	Alkaline reagent Test	–
Flavonoid	Alkaline reagent Test	+
Carbohydrate	Benedict Test	+
Total Phenolic	Ferric chloride test	+
Proteins	Biuret Test	+

Anthocyanins are classified under the flavonoid group of polyphenol compounds, which gives rise to the red and blue colours of vegetables, fruits, flowers, and leaves.^[1] Anthocyanins are present in plants as a glycoside in which the anthocyanidin is bound to a sugar group, with glucose, galactose, rhamnose, xylose, or arabinose bound to an aglycon.^[12] Compounds reported to be found in the flowers are ternatin anthocyanins and various flavanol glycosides of kaempferol, quercetin and myricetin.^[4] Analyzing reports, article and research paper based on phytochemical analysis *Clitoria ternatea* and our research work shows presence of bioactive compounds and phytoconstituent such as, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins, and absence of tannin which are helpful in various treatment can be used as medicinal factor.

Colour absorption property measured in colorimeter at different wavelength in the range 400-700nm

The colour absorption properties of the three extracts – aqueous extract (1 hour), reflux extract, and aqueous extract (7 days) – were measured using a colorimeter at different wavelengths ranging from 400 to 700 nm. All three extracts showed measurable absorbance within this visible range. Among them, seven days aqueous extraction exhibited the highest absorbance values across most wavelengths, indicating a greater concentration of colour compounds. The aqueous extract (1 days) showed moderate absorbance, while the reflux extract (1 hour) recorded the lowest absorbance values in comparison as shown in fig.2.

Fig. 2: Graphical representation of colour absorbance at different wavelength.

Antimicrobial activity by agar well diffusion method

The antibacterial profile of *Clitoria ternatea* and standard compound (Penecillin 1mg/ml) was determined by calculating zone of inhibition against Gram negative (*E. coli*) and Gram positive (*St. aureus*) bacterial strains through well diffusion technique. Compared to the conventional penecillin, demonstrated moderate activity. In comparison to penecillin, the antimicrobial activities of *Clitoria ternatea* differed significantly. *Clitoria ternatea* exhibited comparatively lesser activity against *E. coli* & *St. aureus* than penicillin.

Table 2: Zone of Inhibition of std. and ethanolic extract against bacteria.

Organism	Zone of inhibition(std)	Zone of inhibition(Ethanolic extract)
<i>S.aureus</i>	12mm	5mm
<i>E.coli</i>	10mm	3mm

Based on the previous studies that reported the benefits of Butterfly pea flower, the goal of this study is to analysis the antibacterial activity of Medan butterfly pea corolla extract against *S. mutans* ATCC®25175™ and *S. aureus* ATCC®6538™. The assessment of antibacterial was based on antibiofilm activities and membrane cell leakage of DNA, protein, calcium, and potassium ions.^[13]

The water-based extract of butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) petals significantly improved color characteristics, total phenolic content, total anthocyanin content, and antimicrobial activity. The flowers of the butterfly pea, especially the petals, are a vivid deep blue color.

They contain high amounts of anthocyanin, a phenolic compound containing flavonoid groups. This compound is water-soluble and can produce blue, purple, red, and orange colors. The flowers have various biological activities, including anti-diabetic, anti-pyretic, anti-helminthic, anti-leprosy, anti-asthmatic, anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-fungal, anti-depressant, anti-convulsant, and analgesic activities.^[12,14, 15, and 16]

Photographs of dyed cloth

Cotton Cloth was dyed using three different extracts and its dyeing properties were observed as follows:- The dye is then used in the cotton fabric for the fixation of color.

Fig. 3: Cloth dyed using aqueous extract.

Fig. 4: Cloth dyed using Reflux extract.

Fig. 5: Cloth dyed using 1hr aqueous extract.

All the aqueous extract were used to stain cotton cloth and the result indicated that all are having staining property which is shown in Fig 3,4,5.

Natural dyes are extracted from plants, and they are biodegradable and non-toxic. Unlike synthetic dyes, which are made from petroleum-based chemicals and are harmful to the environment, natural dyes do not cause pollution.^[10] These dyes are eco-friendly and non-toxic, making them a safer alternative to synthetic dyes. They have the potential to effectively replace synthetic dyes and help mitigate the environmental pollution they cause in water and soil. However, the dyed fabric tends to fade after exposure to sunlight for 48 hours and subsequent washing. To address this limitation, future studies should focus on improving dye stability by introducing more effective mordants or fixative agents.

CONCLUSION

Natural dyes extracted from pea flowers not only stain cotton but also significant antimicrobial properties, which could be harnessed in a variety of industries. The phytochemical analysis revealed that compounds such as flavonoids, proteins, total phenolics, and carbohydrates anthraquinones play a vital role in both dyeing and antimicrobial activities. This study highlights the potential of natural dyes as a sustainable, bioactive alternative to synthetic dyes, with applications in textiles, medicine, and food preservation. Further research into their mechanisms of action and long-term stability is recommended to fully realize their potential in practical applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Sincere thanks to Principal Dr. B.P.Ladgaonkar Smt. Kasturbai Walachand Arts and Science College, Sangli for providing facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Singh, R., & Srivastava, S. Exploration of flower based natural dyes – A review. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 2015; 4(IVC-2015): 6-8.
2. Kalyani, T. G., & Rafeekher, M. A comprehensive review on extraction techniques for natural dyes from flowers. *International Journal of Advanced Biochemistry Research*, 2025; 9(2): 403–407.
3. Mukherjee, P. K., Kumar, V., Kumar, N. S., & Heinrich, M. The Ayurvedic medicine *Clitoria ternatea* – From traditional use to scientific assessment. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 2008; 120(3): 291–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2008.08.021>
4. Sushmitha, G. R. A review note on butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications*, 2024; 9(2): 975–981.
5. ChibuyeBitwella, Singh SenIndra, Chimuka Luke, Maseka Kenneth KakomA review of modern and conventional extraction techniques and their applications for extracting phytochemicals from plants, *Scientific African*, 2023; 1-19.
6. Geetha, B., & Sumathy, V. J. H. Extraction of natural dyes from plants. *International Journal of Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013; 1(8): 502–509.
7. Khandelwal KR. 2nd ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan, Practical Pharmacognosy, 2009.
8. Kokate CK. Delhi: New Gyan Offset Printers, Practical Pharmacognosy, 2000.
9. Sashikala, S., Iffath, A. N., & Sharmila, S. Extraction of natural dyes from some plant parts and its applications on fabrics. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 2024; 12(3): [IJCRT2403410].
10. Kombey, P., Rai, K., & Chaudhary, V. Natural dyes extracted from flower crops: A review of recent advances. *European Chemical Bulletin*, 2023; 12(5): 5110–51.
11. Chungkrang, L., Bhuyan, S., & Rani, A. Natural dyes: Extraction and applications. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 2021; 10(1): [https://doi.org/\[Insert DOI if available\]](https://doi.org/[Insert DOI if available])
12. Jeyaraj, Ethel & Lim, Yau & Choo, Wee-Sim. Antioxidant, cytotoxic, and antibacterial activities of *Clitoria ternatea* flower extracts and anthocyanin-rich fraction. *Scientific Reports*, 2022; 12: 10.1038/s41598-022-19146-z.

13. Satria, D., Sofyanti, E., Wulandari, P., Fajarini, Pakpahan, S. D., & Limbong, S. A. Antibacterial activity of Medan butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) corolla extract against *Streptococcus mutans* ATCC®25175™ and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC®6538™. *Pharmacia*, 2022; 69(1): 195–202.
14. Chakraborty, G. S., Kumar, V., Gupta, S., Kumar, A., Gautam, N., & Kumari, L. Phytochemical and pharmacological aspects of *Clitoria ternatea* – A review. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 1(2): 03–09.
15. 15.Kumar, S. R., Sherief, S. H., Tawale, H., Chavan, A. B., Mohammed, J. S., Latha, C. M., Jayalekshmi, R., Biju, C., Borse, G. N., & Gupta, V. L. A comprehensive evaluation of *Clitoria ternatea*: Its botanical description, phytochemistry, pharmacological activities, and traditional uses. *African Journal of Biological Sciences*, 2024; 6(14): [https://doi.org/\[Insert DOI if available\]](https://doi.org/[Insert DOI if available])
16. Dubey, V., Gupta, P., & Jaiswal, J. K. Exploring the antimicrobial potential of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves: A comprehensive review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications*, 2023; 8(5): 936–947.